

Design and Development of Milling Attachment for CNC Turning Center

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Abstract— A milling attachment has been developed and installed in the existing Computer Numerical Control (CNC) turning center using conceptual design CNC machine operates on mechatronic controls and a computer interface. The CNC machine becomes multifunctional with the presently developed milling attachment and can be used both for milling and drilling operations. It is a compact, portable unit capable of doing many milling operations that normally require expensive single-purpose machines. This self-powered, vertical-feed, variable-speed precision tool may be mounted in any position on the carriage, table, ram, turret, or tool arm of other machine tools. The vibration analysis and surface roughness testing have been carried and the results were found satisfactory.

Keywords — CNC machine, milling attachment, microprocessor.

I. INTRODUCTION

Computer Numerical Control (CNC) milling machines are milling machines in which the cutter path is controlled by numerical data rather than a physical template. They are especially suited to profile milling, pocket milling, surface contouring and die sinking operations, in which two or three axes of the worktable must be simultaneously controlled to achieve the required cutter path. An operator is normally required to change cutters as well as load and unload work parts. The mill turn lathes are invaluable when part tolerances are critical and floor space is limited. The mill turn lathes preserve accuracy and surface finish, because the process enables seamless integration of an operation so will not be losing accuracy or wasting time with multiple setups. The concept of a new product includes product requirements, functions possible behaviours, form/structure and associated properties. Properties include material, assembly level tolerance, critical surface roughness and hardness parameters and critical dimension Conceptual design and development process accelerates the process of prototype design and development. It is supported by creativity which leads to generation of new and valued/ innovative ideas. Some work has been carried out on Multiaxis Machining with Additional-

Axis NC System [1]. Four and five axis machining is advanced technology for dealing with complex shaped parts but its application is restricted owing to the high investment cost. The additional-axis method, typically obtained by attaching a rotary/tilt table to an existing three-axis machine, is a powerful alternative for achieving multiaxis machining. And previous research reveals that [2] development of Lathe Attachment for a CNC Machine. A lathe attachment has been developed for an existing CNC machine (installed with rapid prototyping attachment) using conceptual design. In Interference-Free Tool-Path Planning for Flank Milling of Twisted Ruled Surfaces, flank milling is the key feature that the five-axis NC machine offers. Compared with bottom-edge based machining, the machinability can be greatly enhanced by flank milling where the side cutting edge is mainly used[3]. As far as tool-path planning is concerned, the conventional method of the cutter-axis parallel to the ruling lines of the generator curves imposes interference problems including overcut/undercut. In Production of Form Surfaces by CNC Milling Machine Tool, production of form surfaces increases the demands on productivity and machining precision[4]. Therefore, there is the need to implement CAM production systems. There is new type of CNC machine tool interpolator that is capable of generating the cutter path for ball-end milling of a freeform surface[5]. The surface interpolator comprises on-line algorithms for cutter-contact (CC) path scheduling, CC path interpolation, and tool offsetting. In dimensional and geometrical errors of three-axis CNC milling machines in a virtual machining system, virtual machining systems are applying computers and different types of software in manufacturing and production in order to simulate and model errors of real environment in virtual reality systems[6]

II. METHODOLOGY

The milling attachment was designed and fabricated for a CNC turning centre and the steps involved in carrying out the proposed work are described below

A. Problem Identification

Existing Computer Numerical Control (CNC) turning center is capable of performing only turning and if the component requires both turning and milling then it need to be shifted to another machine. This process is time consuming and hence it is required to integrate the milling attachment to the CNC lathe in order to carry out both turning and milling operation on a same machine.

B. Study of the Existing CNC Machine

In the existing CNC machine (Figure 1) only turning operation was carried out. Control system is FANUC Oi-Mate-TD. Its capacity between centre lengths is 280mm, maximum machining diameter is 140mm, maximum turning length is 200mm and optimum turning diameter is 80mm. The spindle speeds in full power range is 1000-3000 rpm, whereas standard spindle speed is 4000rpm. The maximum bar capacity is 25 mm. The work holding standard chuck size is 135 mm. The number of stations is 8 wherein the milling attachment was replaced instead of one among many turning tools. The maximum bore diameter is 32mm

Fig 1. CNC machine

C. Milling Attachment

The attachment consists of the following component

Bracket

The bracket was designed with respect to the axis for holding the motor to the tool station.

Micro controlled motor assembly

The motor selected has parameters of 1440 rpm which is a single phase induction motor with the maximum output of 40W. The current utilized by the motor is 0.5A and the voltage of 200V. The frequency of the motor operated in the range 50-60 Hz. AT mega 328 microcontroller is used to control the operations of the attachment as shown in the figure 2

Fig 2. Electronic circuit board

Operations carried out using microcontroller are, turning the motor ON/OFF and changing the direction.

Adapter

The spindle adapters are used to adapt arbors and milling cutters to the standard tapers used for milling machine spindles. With the proper spindle adapters, any tapered or straight shank cutter or arbor can be fitted to any milling machine, if the sizes and tapers are standard.

Collar / Reduction bush

The collar/reduction bush is a cylindrical feature on a part fitted with a shaft used to prevent sliding (axial) movement.

Drill chuck

The drill chuck is used on tools ranging from professional equipment to inexpensive hand and power drills for domestic use.

The above mentioned components of the milling attachment were prepared and the assembly of these components resulting in a proposed milling attachment.

D. Milling Operation using Milling Attachment

The milling operation was carried on certain samples made of different materials like mild steel, aluminium, copper and brass. In the milling attachment different operations such as horizontal keyways, tapered slots and splined profile were performed. The machined samples were subjected to surface roughness test for further validation and vibration analysis was carried out during the milling operation on CNC turning centre

E. Machine Performance Test

The performance of the machine usually depends on the vibration levels of the machine at different locations. The vibration levels were detected with help of instrument called Shock Pulse Meter (SPM). The vibration levels at different locations were noted and further analysed. If the obtained results were unsatisfactory, then further analysis with more sophisticated instrument is necessary. The figure 3 represents the method of checking the vibration levels.

Figure 3. Vibration level recording using SPM

III. FABRICATION OF MILLING ATTACHMENT

The fabrication steps followed in the work is explained in the following; the existing CNC machine was capable of performing only turning operation. However, the attachment of milling apparatus will be leading to perform milling operation also. Bracket was designed with reference to the machine centre axis from the existing CNC machine. Bracket was initially designed as a flat rectangular plate. However later on the flat plate was machined to the required dimensions by omitting irregular shape

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

A. Vibration Analysis

The following sections illustrate the vibration analysis carried out during the milling operations using the developed attachment on a CNC turning center

Vibration Level at No Load Condition

Initially at no load condition the readings are taken in all the 3 directions i.e. horizontal, axial and vertical and the results are tabulated in table 1

Table 3.1 Vibration level at no load condition

<i>Vibration level (mm/sec)</i>		
<i>Horizontal</i>	<i>Vertical</i>	<i>Axial</i>
0.2	0.3	0.3
0.2	0.3	0.3
0.2	0.3	0.3

0.2	0.3	0.3
0.2	0.3	0.3
0.2	0.3	0.3

Fig.4: Vibration level at no load condition

Vibration Level in Horizontal Direction

Table 2 Vibration level in horizontal direction for different materials

<i>Vibration level (mm/sec)</i>			
<i>Aluminium</i>	<i>Mild Steel</i>	<i>Brass</i>	<i>Copper</i>
0.8	0.5	0.4	1.5
1	1.1	0.3	1.1
0.4	1	0.3	1
0.4	0.9	0.4	0.9
0.4	0.7	0.6	1
0.4	0.3	0.3	0.9

Fig.5:Vibration level in horizontal direction

Vibration Level in Vertical Direction

Table3 shows the vibration level recorded in vertical direction for different material.

Table 3 shows the vibration level recorded in vertical direction for different material.

Sl.no	Vibration level (mm/sec)			
	Aluminium	Mild Steel	Brass	Copper
1	0.5	0.9	0.7	1.5
2	0.5	3.3	1.6	2.2
3	1.3	2.8	1.2	1.9
4	1.2	2.7	1.3	2
5	1.3	2.9	1.3	2.1
6	1.2	2.9	1.2	1.8

Fig.5:Vibration level in vertical direction

Vibration Level in Axial Direction

Table 4 shows the vibration level recorded in axial direction for different material.

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Sl.no	Vibration level (mm/sec)			
	Aluminium	Mild Steel	Brass	Copper
1	0.4	1.1	0.4	1
2	0.4	1	0.5	1.6
3	0.5	0.8	0.5	0.8
4	0.5	0.9	0.5	0.7
5	0.5	0.8	0.5	0.7
6	0.5	0.9	0.6	0.7

Fig.6:Vibration level in Axial direction

From the table 1 to 4 we can notice that, in horizontal, vertical and axial directions low vibration levels were observed in aluminium and brass compared to mild steel and copper. But the vibrations of copper and mild steel are well within the limit. Hence aluminium and brass are preferable for this setup.

B. Surface Roughness

The surface roughness was compared conventional milling machine and the milling attachment for aluminium, mild steel, brass and copper. The surface roughness test was carried out in Perfect Alloy Components, Shivamogga. The measuring conditions in which surface roughness carried out is mentioned in table 5

Table 5: Measuring conditions carried out for surface roughness

Standard	ISO 97
Measuring length	6.000
Unit	Mm
Cut-off	Gaussian
Cut-off wavelength	0.8
Measuring range	80µm

Roughness measurement of the slot

Ra – Average Roughness Also known as Arithmetic Average (AA), Center Line Average (CLA), Arithmetical Mean Deviation of the profile. The average roughness is the area between the roughness profile and its mean line, or the integral of the absolute value of the roughness profile height over the evaluation length.

Figure 7. Roughness profile along the length of the tool

The table 5 shows the roughness values of the slot produced on different materials by conventional milling machine

Table 5 Roughness values of the slot by conventional milling machine

Material	Ra (in μm)
Mild Steel	3.687
Aluminium	0.418
Brass	0.184
Copper	0.466

Fig 8 Graph shows slot roughness for conventional milling machine

Roughness of the Slot produced by CNC with milling attachment

Table 6 shows the slot roughness of the materials conducted on CNC with milling attachment.

Table 6 Slot roughness for CNC with milling attachment

Material	Ra (in μm)
Mild Steel	1.641
Aluminium	0.764
Brass	0.859
Copper	0.869

Fig 9 Graph shows slot roughness for CNC with milling attachment

As mentioned in the figure 6, the graph shows the slot roughness of the specimen machined under CNC with milling attachment and it can be seen that the surface roughness of the steel specimen was less compared to that of conventional machining method. However the aluminium, brass and copper made specimens have less surface roughness. Conventional milling machine and it can be seen that the surface roughness of the steel specimen was more compared to aluminium, brass and copper made specimens. However the aluminium and brass made specimens have less surface roughness

V. CONCLUSIONS

The following conclusions are drawn from the present work which involves the design and development of milling attachment for a CNC turning center:

- Milling operations can be performed in the existing CNC turning center, in which only turning operation was able to carry out earlier.
- The performance of the proposed work was validated by vibration analysis using comparative analysis where in the results yields the vibration levels within the acceptable limit.
- The result concludes that the present work is more suitable for milling of the aluminium and brass materials.
- The milling on mild steel and copper materials shows slightly more vibration levels in the attachment compared to aluminium and brass materials.

- Comparing the surface roughness of specimen machined by the milling attachment on turning center and that of conventional milling machine, the slot roughness of the materials are in between average achievable roughness and finer.

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